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Title: "Behavior of provisional pressure-reducing materials in diabetic foot"

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Abstract: Objective: The main aim of this work is to assess the behavior of felts of latex foam, wool, wool on latex and 10 mm polyurethane foam as provisional pressure-reducing materials compared to foot hyperpressures. Secondary aims are to determine how Body Mass Index and Physical activity impact the pressure-reducing capacity of these materials. The research hypothesis sets out that there are statistically significant differences between the pressure-reducing capacity of the different materials and that they are impacted by Body Mass Index and Physical Activity. Research Design and Methods: This study was descriptive, correlational and experimental. The sample was comprised of 32 subjects, 64 feet aged between 19 and 76 years, with plantar hyperpressures of different etiologies. The pressure was assessed using the platform pressures. Results: The results revealed an effective reduction of pressures for all materials; this was more durable for polyurethane. Conclusions: It was concluded that pressure-reducing materials are effective on the reduction of hyperpressures but there are differences between them as to duration of the effect.

Suggested Reviewers:

Opposed Reviewers:

Response to Reviewers:

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Dear D. Bader,

Please consider the manuscript entitled “Behavior of provisional pressure-reducing materials in diabetic foot”. In this paper we present one of the first studies where different types of felts are compared to reduce plantar pressure. This study goes along the same lines of the magazine, since the main goal is to cure pressure ulcers. In light of total contact cast being the gold standard technique, which I am sure you are familiar with, we seek less invasive alternatives to decrease plantar pressure and consequently increase the therapeutic options.

In this sense, we believe it might provide useful data to the research on healing neuropathic diabetic foot ulcers. Therefore, we are convinced the submitted manuscript is a contribution of great interest to different health professions.

For this reason, we consider Journal of Tissue Viability to be the most suitable journal to publish this study, considering our main purpose is wound-healing and to improve patients’ quality of life.

All authors were fully involved in the study and preparation of the manuscript. The present manuscript has not been published or submitted to any other journal. MPC, MRB and JMJJ did participate in data collection; MPC and MRB did participate in data analysis, data interpretation, and writing of the manuscript; MCJ did participate in writing of the manuscript; JMJJ. contributed to the study design, and reviewed the manuscript.

The authors also represents that no benefits in any form have been received or will be received from a commercial party related directly or indirectly to the subject of this article. They have no conflict of interest.

In order to help editor to know about the manuscript, please, allow us to show the abstract:

“The main aim of this work is to assess the behavior of felts of latex foam, wool, wool on latex and 10 mm polyurethane foam as provisional pressure-reducing materials compared to foot hyperpressures for effective healing of ulcers. Secondary aims are to determine how Body Mass Index and Physical activity impact the pressure-reducing capacity of these materials. The research hypothesis sets out that there are statistically significant differences between the pressure-reducing capacity of the different materials and that they are impacted by Body Mass Index and Physical Activity. This study was descriptive, correlational and experimental. The sample was comprised of 32 subjects, 64 feet aged between 19 and 76 years, with plantar hyperpressures of different etiologies. The pressure was assessed using the platform pressures. Results: The results

revealed an effective reduction of pressures for all materials; this was more durable for polyurethane. It was concluded that pressure-reducing materials are effective on the reduction of hyperpressures but there are differences between them as to duration of the effect.”

Sincerely yours ,

Manuel Pabón-Carrasco.

José María Juárez-Jiménez.

María Reina-Bueno

Manuel Coheña-Jiménez

Dear Editor-in-Chief,

Thank you very much for your work, and the reviewers'. We are pleased to have been given the chance to re-submit the manuscript with some changes suggested by the reviewers.

Below you can find the reviewers' comments and authors' response.

Thank you very much for your effort.

Sincerely,

The authors.

Reviewer's comments	Authors' response
1. Tables 1 and 2 present the descriptive statistics both in parametric form (mean, SD) and non-parametrically (median, inter-quarter range. The data is either normally or non-normally distributed - therefore only one set of descriptive statistics is appropriate.	Tables modified based on the comments
2. There is redundancy in Table 3 with p values for paired comparisons repeated in the table. This could be avoided if you combined the comparisons between materials for both data at onset and data at 72 hours.	We combined the comparisons between materials for both data at onset and data at 72 hours.
3. In the statistic analysis section (1.2.3) only the test hypothesis needs to be stated Suggest "The study tests the hypothesis that the materials produce differences in the mean pressures under the foot. Where the group mean differences were found to be statistically significant (p<0.05), a multiple comparison or post-hoc test was performed..."	Added: "The study tests the hypothesis that the materials produce differences in the mean pressures under the foot. Where the group mean differences were found to be statistically significant (p<0.05), a multiple comparison or post-hoc test was performed."
4. Although the pressure measuring device is recorded in units of N/cm ² -this is NOT a SI units. So all the pressure data should be converted to N/m ² . Therefore throughout the text all pressure values should be quoted accordingly. As an example, the hyperpressure threshold should be quoted as 29.4 x10 ⁴ = 294 kPa (2205 mmHg).	Change units N/m ²
5. Units of BMI are kg/m ² NOT Kg/m ²	Change Units of BMI: kg/m ²
6. The discussion involving the performance of the 4 different materials should be integrated, so that it does not include one study findings followed by the next.	The discussion of the 4 different materials is integrated, so that it does not include one study findings followed by the next.

Conflict of interest

All the authors declare that they have no conflict of interest derived from the outcomes of this study.

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Title “Behavior of provisional pressure-reducing materials in diabetic foot”

Short running title “Pressure-reducing materials in diabetic foot”

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Abstract

Objective: The main aim of this work is to assess the behavior of felts of latex foam, wool, wool on latex and 10 mm polyurethane foam as provisional pressure-reducing materials compared to foot hyperpressures. Secondary aims are to determine how Body Mass Index and Physical activity impact the pressure-reducing capacity of these materials. The research hypothesis sets out that there are statistically significant differences between the pressure-reducing capacity of the different materials and that they are impacted by Body Mass Index and Physical Activity. **Research Design and Methods:** This study was descriptive, correlational and experimental. The sample was comprised of 32 subjects, 64 feet aged between 19 and 76 years, with plantar hyperpressures of different etiologies. The pressure was assessed using the platform pressures. **Results:** The results revealed an effective reduction of pressures for all materials; this was more durable for polyurethane. **Conclusions:** It was concluded that pressure-reducing materials are effective on the reduction of hyperpressures but there are differences between them as to duration of the effect.

Keywords: Diabetic Foot; Hyperpressures; Pressure Reduction; Wools

- All different types of felts reduce pressure.
- BMI and physical activity influence differently on the loss of efficacy of the materials.
- Polyurethane provides the best resolution according to the results of this study. ($p = 0,004$)” (Loss of efficacy $0,42 \pm 0,17$).

1.1 Introduction

Diabetic foot remains one of the most significant complications of Diabetes Mellitus. It causes a high number of leg amputations, a high degree of disability, in addition to an increase in the number and cost of hospital admissions (1-5).

Sole hyper-pressures in the foot at risk are reported as one of the causes of onset of difficult to resolve lesions. Currently, there has been major progress over the use of increasingly effective dressings and scarring methods (negative pressure therapy, growth factors, protease modulators, etc.). However, the use of provisional pressure reduction materials has only been partially studied (6). The use of pressure reductions as the main thrust of ulcer treatment of neuropathic or neuroischemic origin is highly beneficial; reducing the hyperpressure in the area leads to modifications to the histology of the lesions, which change from a chronic inflammatory state to a much more favorable condition (7-9). The reduction in pressure has the basic aim of distributing the load over a broader area, so that the hyperpressure peaks over certain points are reduced (10).

There are other studies that evaluate the effectiveness of the felts, in particular wool felts.(11-12)

For this reason, a global study of provisional pressure reduction materials as a more generalized technique for the reduction of hyperpressures, in addition to the impact of the variables Body Mass Index (hereinafter BMI) and Physical Activity on these, is especially noteworthy.

1.2 Research Design and Methods

This study was descriptive, correlational and experimental (13). The sample was comprised of 32 subjects, that is 64 feet, with ages between 19 and 76 years. Each foot or case was considered separately. The software G-Power 3.1.0 (University of Kiel, Kiel, Germany) was used to calculate sample size. For an alpha error of 0.05, a power of 95% and a mean effect size, the minimum number of cases necessary is 34. The pressure reduction material are wools of latex foam, wool, wool on latex and 10 mm-thick polyurethane foam.

1.2.1 Inclusion Criteria

All participants presented type II diabetes. History of plantar ulceration of the foot (increase in pressure) (14-17) or present some kind of prior amputation (predisposes the increase in pressure and restructuring of the foot loads) (16,18-20) or present areas of plantar callus (hyperpressure) (21).

1.2.2 Exclusion Criteria

Have previously received treatment for the plantar hyperpressures: plantar orthosis, foot surgery, shoe therapy, etc. (22-23)

Sample subjects are patients from the Podiatry Clinical Area and Podiatry degree students from University of Seville, who comply with the inclusion criteria and voluntarily agree to take part in the study. This study was authorized by the site's management.

The pressures platform Rss-Scan® (Beringen, Belgium) was used to assess plantar pressure. This was calibrated for each subject, using the patient's weight before each test session. Individuals walked barefoot on the platform to familiarize themselves with the system and to guarantee as natural a gait as possible (24). Subsequently, three barefoot steps for each subject were recorded on the platform, which was quantified in N/m^2 (25-27). The mean maximum pressure was calculated for each one of the 10 areas into which the program splits the foot (the five metatarsals, the first toe, minor toes, mid foot, internal and external heel area). Once the area of maximum pressures was identified, the pressure reduction material was positioned. The man walks barefoot on the platform with the material. High pressure area is considered greater than $294000 N/m^2$. It was covered the sole of the foot and leaving the area of maximum pressure without support. The cut out was corresponded to the size of the overhead area. The diameter of the cut out will depend on the extent of the affected area.

The pressure reduction was prepared by covering the entire foot and leaving the maximum area of pressure without support; this was fixed onto the sole of the foot and reinforced with a cohesive bandage. The original thickness is the same in all materials. Therefore, it cannot be withdrawn by the patient and the edge effect (increased pressure on margins) was reduced (28). The bath is not allowed in 72 hours. Subjects confirmed verbally that had performed the same activity with each material. After inserting the pressure reduction, the pressure was measured.

After 72 hours, three new measurements of the plantar pressures with the subject barefoot were taken to obtain the mean for each one of the pressure reduction area (29). The

reduction in thickness of the material close to the pressure reduction area was reduced by three points. The subject used the same shoe throughout the study so that the conditions were homogeneous. This process was repeated with all pressure reduction materials (wools of latex foam, two presentations of wools presented as 5 mm and one of 10 mm, wool on latex and 10 mm-thick polyurethane foam). All measurements follow the same procedure.

BMI and physical activity were calculated for each subject. The International Physical Activity Questionnaire was used (hereinafter IPAQ) (30).

1.2.3 Statistical Analysis

The analysis was performed with the statistical package SPSS version 18 for Windows (Chicago, USA). The total sample was reported according to age, gender, BMI, physical activity, location and reason for the area of hyperpressure. The degree of reduction of pressures at onset and at 72 hours, in addition to loss of thickness, were determined.

To verify whether the data were normally distributed the Shapiro-Wilk test was used. The Anova and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used for comparison of materials upon immediate placement and at 72 hours, respectively.

The study tests the hypothesis that the materials produce differences in the mean pressures under the foot. Where the group mean differences were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), a multiple comparison or post-hoc test was performed.

Linear regression was performed to assess the degree of relationship of the BMI variables and physical activity in regard to the deterioration of the materials.

1.3 Results

The initial sample was comprised of 32 subjects; two did not complete the study (because of a change in city and for unknown reasons). The final sample was comprised of 30 subjects, 60 feet. A total of 53.3% and 46.7% were women and men, respectively. Mean age was 32.61 ± 15.36 years, ranging from 20 to 75 and mean BMI 23.33 ± 3.38 kg/m², ranging from 17.35 kg/m² to 32.38 kg/m². Physical activity was low, moderate and high in 37.3%, 39.2% and 23.5% of the sample, respectively.

According to area of hyperpressure, 67.3% was located in the II, III and IV metatarsal, 16.1% in the V metatarsal, 10.8% in the I metatarsal and 5.9% in the lesser toes. Maximum dynamic pressures between 31800 and 233400 N/m² were observed; the mean was 125800 ± 49300 N/m². After placing the materials pressures from 7000 to 190000 N/m² and a mean of 48600 ± 32600 N/m² were measured. At 72 hours the pressures were between 9300 and 20900 N/m², with a mean of 68200 ± 40500 N/m².

As for the **loss of thickness** of the materials at 72 hours: for *latex*, the mean was 1.32 ± 0.68 mm (range of 2.5 to 0.3 mm), for *latex-wool*, the mean was 1.60 ± 0.70 mm (range of 2.70 to 0.5 mm), for *polyurethane*, the mean was 0.36 ± 0.13 mm (range of 0.6 to 0.02 mm), for *5 mm wool*, the mean was 2.20 ± 1.00 mm (range of 4.1 to 0.8 mm) and for *10 mm wool*, mean loss was 2.9 ± 1.35 mm (range of 5.1 to 0.8 mm). Percentage pressure reduction at onset and at 72 hours is shown. TABLE 1

The loss of efficacy (TABLE 2) was created with the following formula using the remaining variables: $\left(\frac{(\text{Basal pressure}-\text{Pressure at onset})}{\text{Basal pressure}} \times 100\right) - \left(\frac{(\text{Basal pressure}-\text{Pressure at 72 hours})}{\text{Basal pressure}} \times 100\right)$

At the time of placement of the pressure reductions, the multiple or post-hoc comparison test was performed: Bonferroni Correction ($P \geq 0.05$), which revealed that latex was responsible for this difference; the remaining materials presented a similar pressure-reduction capacity. To compare the results at 72 hours we used the corrected Mann-Whitney U test. Polyurethane behaved differently to the remaining materials, with virtually no loss of capacity for pressure reduction at 72 hours. The latex and wool of 5 mm x 2 behaved in a similar way to the remaining materials except polyurethane. The combined material latex-wool and 10 mm thick wool behaved in a similar way to 5 mm x 2 wool and latex and differently between themselves and in regard to polyurethane. TABLE 3

1.3.1 Impact of BMI and physical activity on the loss of efficacy of the materials

It was established whether the loss of efficacy was directly related to the deterioration in the material (loss of thickness). The goodness of fit of the regressions was quite high except for the polyurethane (Goodness of fit, R squared corrected 0,395).

A linear regression was performed to observe whether the variable “loss of efficacy” depends on BMI. There was a direct relationship between BMI and loss of efficacy of the materials; this was greater for materials that contained wool and lower for latex or polyurethane. Sig. BMI $\leq 0,05$ and Goodness of fit Latex= 0.312, Latex-Wool=0.507, Polyurethane=0.188, Wool 5 mm (x2)= 0.738, Wool 10 mm=0.747.

In relation to physical activity and its impact on the deterioration of the material, three fictitious and bivariate materials were created: high, moderate and low physical activity. A multiple regression with a constant statistic, a qualitative variable (physical activity) and a quantitative variable (BMI) was performed. TABLE 4

In reference to high physical activity we obtained a direct relationship with loss of efficacy; this was greater for brushed wool felts and lesser for polyurethane ($P \leq 0.05$). Moderate physical activity exclusively affected the materials with a wool component. Low physical activity was a protective factor because the activity was recorded as negative.

1.4 Discussion

There are few published studies that rigorously tackle the behavior of the different provisional pressure reduction materials used in diabetic feet, and the impact on the efficacy of the pressure reduction determined by variables such as the patient's BMI and physical activity.

Fleischli et al. performed a comparison in 1997 with multiple pressure reduction treatments, including provisional felts; they obtained a load reduction of between 34% and 48% (31). In 2001, Zimny et al. assessed the effects of wool felts on the reduction of plantar pressure during treatment of ulcers in neuropathic feet. Their aim was to define the material's lifetime and they assessed felts at onset and up to day 4. Their results coincide with this study both at onset and at 72 hours. They conclude that the wools reduce pressure initially but quickly lose efficacy in regard to their wear; this is reflected in the loss of thickness (32).

In 2003, Lázaro et al. assessed the pressure reduction felts and obtained a 40% reduction in pressure; this data is much less than that of this study. This coincides with the results obtained at 72 h (33). In 2000, Hissik et al. in a study on diabetic patients with neuropathic ulcers treated with a fiberglass sole shoe and pressure reduction with wool felts of 8 mm obtained an average healing rate of 34 days for 91% of lesions (11). Byrke et al. performed a study on 120 diabetics with forefoot ulcers with neuropathic component in 2002; they compared several pressure reduction strategies. They performed this with felt of 6 mm, which covered the entire forefoot except the ulcerated area. The percentage and healing time for lesions did not differ according to pressure reduction time (34).

In 2007, Morales et al. performed a study on the impact of BMI and physical activity on different materials. They found that BMI is related to wear; however physical activity was unrelated. This may be because their study population, unlike the sample, was mainly sedentary (35). However, some authors attribute the wool a certain elasticity (36); this material has little capacity for recovery. Currently, a materials compression test is being performed by our research team which justifies the provisional behavior of the wool as supported by some authors (30-31). As these open, the material extends, loses thickness and, therefore, efficacy. The difference between similar thicknesses of wool is attributed to the fact that the 10 mm presentation is less compact, which makes it more vulnerable to shear or friction forces. Subjects confirmed verbally that had performed the same activity with each material.

Based on studies in regard to wool (11,32-33) it was observed that the behavior of the latex differs. This presents efficacy upon initial pressure reduction lower than wool and at 72 hours it suffers a more reduced deterioration. Because this is a material with an intercellular bond matrix this gives it a certain structural stability compared to shear or friction forces. This material can be useful to cushion the immediate impact on specific areas, but not to perform timely pressure reductions because of its low capacity to tolerate forces. It presents a small loss of efficacy related to lower dependence of factors such as BMI and physical activity, when compared to wool materials.

Latex-Wool is a hybrid material that combines the two previous provisions (capacity for pressure reduction thanks to the physical peak of the compact wool and more absorption of the impact; more durability because of less wear of the latex). This study reveals that this material can be a useful alternative to wool because it combines the two advantages shown by the previous materials.

Polyurethane provides the best provision according to the results of this study. This is in accordance with the little loss of thickness and its low relationship with BMI and physical activity. During clinical observations, it was recorded that 66.7% of subjects present discomfort and intolerance to the material for reasons of pain in the area, leading to load transfer syndrome. During the compression tests being undertaken, this material reflects viscoelastic behavior; however, since they are comprised of three layers this gives it a very rigid behavior leading to impact peaks.

1.5 Conclusions

1. Wool felts are continuously renewed materials because of their high deterioration impacted by factors such as the subject's BMI and physical activity; this is more obvious in 10 mm-thick wool than in the application of two 5 mm wools.

2. Polyurethane felts are the materials that lose less thickness. However, 10 mm thicknesses are ruled out as they lead to pain in the areas adjacent to the pressure reduction; this is a material with the possibility of being useful with less thickness because of its mechanical resistance over time.
3. Latex felts only reduce pressures initially as they are quickly deformed by their low rigidity and they are not recommended as a first choice pressure reduction material.
4. Combined latex-wool felts present a good capacity for pressure reduction and reveal the appropriateness of searching for a less provisional material than wool that has its same effects.
5. The variables BMI and physical activity have a direct impact on the materials; this is greater for materials with brushed wool.

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TABLE 1. Percentage of pressure reduction at onset and at 72 hours

	Percentage of pressure reduction at onset		Percentage of pressure reduction at 72 hours	
	Mean	Typical deviation	Mean	Typical Deviation
Latex	56.61	5.91	48.25	6.89
Latex-Wool	69.87	4.87	53.18	10.04
Polyurethane	71.62	4.25	71.24	4.35
Wool 5 mm (x2)	71.88	5.15	49.88	13.02
Wool 10 mm (x2)	69.75	5.00	45.27	14.78

TABLE 2. Percentage loss of efficacy at 72 hours

	Mean	Typical deviation
Latex	8.8	1.87
Latex-Wool	16.62	6.63
Polyurethane	0.41	0.18
Wool 5 mm (x2)	21.97	9.61
Wool 10 mm (x2)	24.47	11.15

TABLE 3. Comparison between the different materials and comparison of the materials at 72 hours from their placement. P value above 0.05 suggests similar behavior of materials.

	Percentage of pressure reduction at onset P value	Comparison of the materials at 72 hours P value
Latex Latex-Wool	0.001	0.056
Latex Polyurethane	0.001	0.004
Latex Wool 5 mm (x2)	0.001	0.371
Latex Wool 10 mm (x2)	0.001	0.480
Latex-Wool Polyurethane	1.000	0.004
Latex-Wool Wool 5 mm (x2)	0.789	0.136
Latex-Wool Wool 10 mm (x2)	1.000	0.004
Polyurethane Wool 5 mm (x2)	1.000	0.004
Polyurethane Wool 10 mm (x2)	1.000	0.004
Wool 10 mm (x2) Wool 5 mm (x2)	0.510	0.276

TABLE 4. Relationship between loss of thickness, BMI and physical activity

	Latex	Latex-Wool	Polyurethane	Wool 5 mm (x2)	Wool 10 mm (x2)
Sig. BMI	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Sig. High physical activity	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Goodness of fit (R squared corrected)	0.702	0.712	0.667	0.832	0.885
Sig. Moderate physical activity	0.09	0.04	0.67	0.04	0.05
Goodness of fit (R squared corrected)	0.345	0.446	0.183	0.750	0.753
Sig. Low physical activity	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Goodness of fit (R squared corrected)	0.805	0.821	0.585	0.875	0.897

Graphics 1: Attachment Method by cohesive bandage.

Behavior of provisional pressure-reducing materials in diabetic foot

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